

ISic0013

I.Sicily inscription 0013

Language

Latin

Type

honorific

Material

limestone

Object

base

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

Jonathan Prag,James Cummings,James Chartrand,Valeria Vitale,Michael Metcalfe,Tuuli Ahlholm,Simona Stoyanova

Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Panhormus

Place of origin (modern)

Palermo

Provenance**Coordinates****Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Palermo, Museo Archeologico
Regionale Antonino Salinas, inventory 3513

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

1. Iuliae Aug(ustae)
2. Imp(eratoris) · Caes(aris) · L(uci) Septi
3. mi · Severi · Pertina
4. cis · Aug(usti) · Pii · Parthi
5. ci · Arabici · et · Par
6. thici · Adiabeni
7. ci · p(ontificis) · m(aximi) · tr(ibunicia) · pot(estate) · III
8. imp(eratoris) · V · co(n)s(ulis) · II · p(atris) · p(atriciae)
9. res · publ(ica) · Panhormi
10. tanorum

Apparatus

Text of ILMusPalermo

Translation (en)

To Julia Augusta, (wife) of Emperor Caesar Lucius Septimius Severus Pertinax Augustus Pius, victor in Parthia, Arabia and Parthia Adiabene, pontifex

maximus, holding tribunician power for the third time, imperator for the fifth, consul for the second, Father of Fatherland. (Erected by) the citizens of Panhormus.

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 491774

EDR 137649

EDCS 22000858

Bibliography

Mommsen, Th. 1883. *Inscriptiones Bruttiorum Lucaniae Campaniae Siciliae Sardiniae Latinae. Pars posterior. Inscriptiones Siciliae et Sardiniae. Corpus Inscriptionum Latinarum, consilio et auctoritate Academiae Litterarum Regiae Borussicae editum.* Berlin. At 10.7272 (<http://arachne.uni-koeln.de/item/buchseite/650788>)

Bivona, L. 1970. *Iscrizioni latine lapidarie del Museo di Palermo. Sikelia.* Palermo. At 13

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